

A Survey on Sentiment Analysis Tools and Methods

Adamu Adamu Habu¹

S.K. Alaramma²

B.I. Ya'u²

S.W. Mustapha²

M. A. Musa²

University of St Andrews, Jack
Cole Building, North Haugh, St
Andrews, KY16 9SX, UK

Department of Computer Science,
Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria
kabsunne@gmail.com,
+234-813-8585-559

Abstract

Data has become the currency of this era and is continually increasing in size and value. The available data online is doubling in size very rapidly. The advancement of web technology and its growth has seen a huge volume of data present in the web for internet users. Internet has become a platform for online learning, exchanging ideas and sharing opinions. Social networking sites like Twitter, Facebook, Google+ are rapidly gaining popularity as they allow people to share and express their views about topics, discussion with different communities, or post messages across the world. There have been a number of researches in the field of sentiment analysis solely focusing on social media data. This survey centres mainly on tools and techniques used in sentiment analysis for analyzing information in social media where opinions are highly unstructured, heterogeneous and are positive, negative, or neutral in some cases. In this paper, we provide a survey and a comparative analysis of existing techniques and tools for opinion mining like machine learning and lexicon-based approaches, together with evaluation metrics. This paper will in addition describe the study on different web resources such as review sites, blogs, discussion forums and news. It also gives overview of tools and application area of sentiment analysis.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis (SA), Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid growth of the internet, millions of people are using social network sites like Facebook, Twitter, Google Plus, etc. to express their emotions, opinion and share views about their daily lives. People share their own thoughts and opinions in regards to their day to day life, business, entertainments, politics etc. While the amount of data online that was generated in 2013 was 4.4 Zettabytes (ZB) it is anticipated that in 2024 data created will reach 67 ZB. Individual users are the main source of these data with 75 percent of overall produced data (Pitsilis et al. 2018).

Big data is characterized by three domains that are called 3'V which are *Variety*, *Velocity*, and *Volume*. Variety means the variation of data available online that include both structured and unstructured data such as emails, videos, audios, images, click streams, logs, posts, search queries. Velocity refers to how the processing and storing of these huge and complex data need to be fast in order to accommodate the increasing and continuous requests. Volume indicates the size of the generated data online as presented previously (Kumar et al. 2018).

Social networks have become popular means for cyber communication among societies. For instance, since the establishment of Twitter in 2006 it has provided the ability to freely, easily, and instantaneously express, and share opinions and feelings in public in an SMS style. Twitter is one of the largest platforms that is full of sentiment. It is a micro blogging site, which contains tweets; each tweet has "140 characters or less". There are over 1 billion Tweets every 72 hours from more than 140 million active users on Twitter (Zimmerman et al. 2018). That make it quintessential example of "big data". This textual data is present on the web in two forms: - facts and opinion (or sentiments). Facts have an objective component but, sentiment is the other textual contents which express subjective characteristics. These contents are mainly opinions, appraisals, attitudes, feeling, thoughts, views and emotions, which form the core of Sentiment Analysis (SA). An opinion given in text can be classified into three categories: - positive, negative and neutral.

Users feelings expressed in social media though has a value to be extracted, is hard to detect. Using big data analytic techniques, the value could be extracted. Big data analytics is the process of analyzing a huge amount of data that includes both structured data (such as data inside databases) and unstructured data (such as data on the web) to get valuable information that can be used for taking decisions through the use of advanced analysis techniques such as Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning, and Predictive Analytics (Kumar et al., 2018). Sentiment Analysis (SA) is one of the NLP concepts and the field is used in order to extract the sentiment out of text giving useful information about the author and his/her tendency towards a specific topic (Biere and Bhulai, 2018).

More often than not, and especially on social network platforms, people tend to formulate opinions on a diversity of topics: reviews, ratings, recommendations, among other forms of

online expression. Identifying the sentiment(s) behind these opinions usually turns out to be useful in extracting insights from the data. Sentiment analysis can be defined as a process that automates mining of attitudes, opinions, views and emotions from text, speech, tweets and database sources through Natural Language Processing (NLP). The main idea behind sentiment analysis is to detect any positive and/or negative words or expressions, relying heavily on the direct meaning of words (Stammbach *et al.*, 2018). Opinions in text therefore, are label into categories like "positive" or "negative" or "neutral". It is also referred as subjectivity analysis, opinion mining, and appraisal extraction. Sentiment Analysis as a term includes many tasks such as sentiment extraction, sentiment classification, and subjectivity classification, summarization of opinions or opinion spam detection, among others. It aims to analyze people's sentiments, attitudes, opinions emotions, etc. towards elements such as, products, individuals, topics, organizations, and services.

This paper proposes a survey on some of the works that have been done in the area of sentiment analysis, the tools and the methods used to carry out the study. The paper will discuss the following: Within Section 2 general process flow of sentiment analysis is depicted, describing the process of sentiment analysis in general. This section further includes four subsections: Section 2.1, the data collecting process is described along with the pre-processing techniques used for data cleaning. Section 2.2, gives a deep insight on the techniques that are used to extract features to be analysed. Then, Section 2.3 shows how the model training process works. Section 2.4, describes all the used classification tools, algorithms and performance matrices. Section 3 will review the challenges faced in identifying the sentiment of a text in social media. After that, Section 4 discuss the available tools for sentiment analysis in social media since there is absence of dedicated tools for the task. Section 5 discusses the arears of applications of sentiment analysis. Finally, Section 6 is the conclusion of the survey.

2. TECHNIQUES/APPROACHES FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Sentiment Analysis generally consists of workflow presented in figure 1 below.

Figure 1 General process flow of sentiment analysis

Following are the phases required for sentiment analysis (SA) of social media data

2.1 Pre-processing of the Datasets

The text documents contain rich textual information such as words and phrases, punctuation, abbreviation, emoticons etc. They also tend to have misspelling, duplicate-characters (such as “cool”), especially for social media text. Direct application of SA methods on such text usually leads to poor performance. Therefore, pre-processing is typically conducted to convert the text into textual features that could be fit into the SA methods. Once the pre-processed text features are extracted, they are ready to be fit in the next phase of SA – Feature Selection (Watanabe et al., 2018). Pre-processing is usually based on NLP techniques such as tokenization (splitting the sentences into words), de-noising (remove special characters, capture symbols for emotions), normalization (remove duplicate characters, identify root words etc.), stop-words removal (remove the stop words and the words which are of no use to sentiment analysis), stemming (return the word to its stem or root),

lemmatization (convert inflected words to their root form) etc. The raw data having polarity is highly susceptible to inconsistency and redundancy (Zimmerman *et al.*, 2018). Pre-processing include following points:

- a) **Tokenization:** is defined as slicing a stream of text into pieces, denoted as tokens. The tokenization varies from language to language but lexical characteristics such as colloquialism (e.g. "u" instead of "you"), contractions (e.g. "aren't" instead of "are not") and others (e.g. "O'Neil) make the task harder. This is the most common pre-processing technique used by recent publications: Pitsilis *et al.* (2018), Watanabe *et al.* (2018), Zimmerman *et al.* (2018), Zhang *et al.* (2018), Biere and Bhulai (2018), Kumar *et al.* (2018), Scheffler *et al.* (2018), Pitsilis *et al.* (2018), Stammbach *et al.* (2018), Risch and Krestel (2018), Wiedemann *et al.* (2018), Schäfer (2018), Unsvåg (2018), Ahluwalia *et al.* (2018) and Sharma and Kshitiz (2018). Upon tokenizing, some authors (Founta *et al.* (2018)) also remove the less frequent tokens of the data.
- b) **Lowercasing:** is the process of converting a stream of text to lowercase. Such technique may improve the performance of the classification since it reduces the dimensionality of the data. Not applying this technique may raise problems such as "tomorrow", "TOMORROW" and "ToMoRroW" being considered different words (Aroyehun and Gelbukh, 2018), (Biere and Bhulai, 2018), (Kumar *et al.*, 2018), (Stammbach *et al.*, 2018), (Mishra *et al.*, 2018a), (Wiedemann *et al.*, 2018), (Lee *et al.*, 2018) (Samghabadi *et al.*, 2018), (Unsvåg, 2018), (Sharma and Kshitiz, 2018) and (Sahay *et al.*, 2018) used this technique.
- c) **Punctuation removal:** punctuation often is not relevant to text classification, so it was removed in Aroyehun and Gelbukh (2018), Bohra *et al.* (2018), Kapoor *et al.* (2018), Nikhil *et al.* (2018), Kumar *et al.* (2018), Stammbach *et al.* (2018), Roy *et al.* (2018), Mathur *et al.* (2018), Ibrohim and Budi (2018) and Sharma and Kshitiz (2018). The role of text pre-processing in sentiment analysis, including online text cleaning, white space removal, expanding abbreviation, stemming, negation and stop words removal has been shown to increase sentiment classification accuracy.
- d) **Irrelevant characters removal:** Irrelevant and/or invalid characters (e.g. "?|%&!"), in which we may also include punctuation, are also typically removed from the text since they do not contribute to the classification task as seen in Watanabe *et al.* (2018), Aroyehun and Gelbukh (2018), Zhang *et al.* (2018), Biere and Bhulai (2018),

Sharma et al. (2018), Stambach et al. (2018), Frenda and Somnath (2018), Schäfer (2018) and Sahay et al. (2018).

- e) **Stemming:** is the process of reducing inflected words to a common base form (e.g. "ponies" turns into "poni" and "cats" into "cat"). Stemming also improves performance by reducing the dimensionality of the data, since the words "fishing", "fished", and "fisher" are treated as the same word "fish". This technique is used in Zhang et al. (2018), Biere and Bhulai (2018), Scheffler et al. (2018), Maitra and Sarkhel (2018), Frenda et al. (2018), Samghabadi et al. (2018), Gaydhani et al. (2018), Sharma and Kshitiz (2018) and Sahay et al. (2018).
- f) **Lemmatization:** although very similar to stemming, lemmatization considers the morphological analysis of the words. While stemming would shorten the words "studies" to "studi" and "studying" to "study", lemmatization would shorten both to "study". It is used in Watanabe et al. (2018), Nikhil et al. (2018), Scheffler et al. (2018), Frenda et al. (2018) and Sharma and Kshitiz (2018).
- g) **Stopwords removal:** stop words are frequently used words that carry no useful meaning (e.g. "a", "and", "this"). Their commonness and lack of meaning makes them useless and eventually bad for classification problems in text. They are removed in Kapoor et al. (2018), Maitra and Sarkhel (2018), Mishra et al. (2018a), Mishra et al. (2018b), Unsvåg (2018), Gaydhani et al. (2018), Sharma and Kshitiz (2018).
- h) **PoS tagging:** Part of speech tagging, more commonly associated with feature extraction, is a technique to extract the part of speech associated with each word of the corpus, grammatically wise. Upon doing so, it might be common to remove words belonging to certain parts of speech that might end up not being so relevant (e.g. pronouns). This is done in Watanabe et al. (2018), Robinson et al. (2018), Scheffler et al. (2018) and Frenda and Somnath (2018).
- i) **Emojies:** are usually either removed as in Kapoor et al. (2018), Kumar et al. (2018), Stambach et al. (2018), Frenda et al. (2018), Ibrahim and Budi (2018)) or translated to their corresponding description, e.g. ':)' is translated to 'smile' as in (Bohra et al. (2018), Mathur et al. (2018), Raiyani et al. (2018)). Keeping emojis might be useful since they usually denote a state of spirit or sentiment.
- j) **Spell checker:** misspelling is quite common especially in online platforms due to their informal nature. Having a spell checker like in Nikhil et al., (2018) might be an

important preprocessing technique to avoid having unidentified or intentionally camouflaged words (e.g. "niggr", "fck").

2.2 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction consists of collecting derived values (features) from the input data (text in this specific scenario) and generating distinctive properties, hopefully, informative and non-redundant, in order to improve the learning and generalization tasks of the machine learning algorithms. Upon their extraction there is usually a subset of features that will contain more relevant information. The outputs of pre-processing are the extracted text features. Many text features are considered for SA: unigram (individual words), bigram (two consecutive words), or n-grams (n consecutive words) and either their presence for binary weighting or their frequency to indicate their relative importance; words and phrases commonly used to express opinions words and phrases commonly used to express intensification of opinions negative words that change the opinion orientation; part-of-speech (POS) to find adjectives that contains opinion information, emoticon (special characters to represent emotions). Many words in the text do not have an impact on the general orientation of it. The pre-processed dataset has many distinctive properties. In the feature extraction method, we extract the aspects from the processed dataset. Later these aspects are used to compute the positive and negative polarity in a sentence which is useful for determining the opinion of the individuals using models like unigram, bigram (Stammach et al., 2018).

Generally speaking, feature selection methods can be categorized into filter methods and wrapper methods. Filter methods rank the features according to certain metric and select the top-ranked features. Wrapper methods, on the contrary, select the best subset of features by generation and evaluation of different subsets with a classifier. Selecting the right features is also a complex task but when done successfully improves the predictive model built by the algorithms. The following subsections describe generally most of the methodologies used to extract features from text and users.

1. **N-grams** By definition, an n-gram is a contiguous sequence of (adjacent) words or letters of length "n" extracted from text (Watanabe, et al. 2018). They may be characterized as word ngrams if they group a sequence of "n" words (Robinson, et al. 2018), or character n-grams if they group a sequence of "n" characters (Aroyehun and Gelbukh, 2018). There are three

different ways to use N-grams as a feature: encode using TFIDF (Term Frequency– Inverse Document Frequency), as seen in Risch and Krestel (2018); and Klubicka and Fernández (2018), using a simple token counter (Sharma, et al. 2018) or encode using a hashing function.

2. **Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TFIDF):** TFIDF is a numerical statistic that measures the importance of a certain word in a data corpus. This might be an important feature in understanding the importance of certain words to express specific types of speech (e.g. "hate") (Sharma, et al. 2018). Additionally, words that typically appear often and carry less meaning (e.g. stop words) are not as prominently considered using such encoding.

3. **Bag of Words (BoW):** Bag of words is a representation of words which disregards grammar and the order of the words in sentences, while keeping multiplicity. Like n-grams, BoW can be encoded using TFIDF, token counter or hashing function (Anagnostou, et al. 2018). Although it is typically used to group textual elements as tokens (Frenda and Somnath, 2018; Pamungkas, et al. 2018; de Gibert, et al. 2018), it can also group other representations such as parts of speech as used in Anzovino et al. (2018).

4. **Part of Speech (POS):** Part of speech tagging, also denominated as word-category disambiguation, consists of labelling words with their grammatical designation (e.g. verb, adjective). The main difficulty in tagging text is that each word doesn't necessarily belong to one category of speech (e.g. "fish" might refer to the animal, noun, or the act of fishing, verb). For this reason, the task of identifying the part of speech is not trivial and the context of the phrase must be considered. PoS tagging is particularly helpful in detecting hate speech in text, since hate discourse often contains (offensive) adjectives (e.g. ugly fat boy) (Scheffler, et al. 2018). This feature is sometimes also combined with sentiment analysis. In Risch et al. (2018), verbs with negative polarity are identified.

Table 1 describes the features related to part of speech tagging combined with others used in sentiment detection in text.

PoS Tagging	Combined Feature	Used in
Presence of verbs with negative polarity	Sentiment	Risch et al. (2018)
Check if verb with negative polarity refers to entity	Sentiment + NER	Risch et al. (2018)
For each PoS that may contain sentiment, replace the token by its PoS + polarity (e.g. 'coward' - adjective_negative)	Sentiment	Watanabe et al. (2018)
Number of adjectives	Semantic	Anzovino et al. (2018)

[Source Field work]

5. **Named Entity Recognition (NER)** Named Entity Recognition aims to extract and classify named entities in text, i.e. identify persons, locations or any other category that may be present. This might be particularly useful in sentiment detection since hate instigators tend to target people, groups or ethnicities (e.g. migrants) (Gambäck and Sikdar, 2017). Identifying entities is also usually combined with sentiment analysis in hate speech detection. As an example, Risch et al. (2018) identifies the entities negatively mentioned.

6. **Word embeddings** Word embeddings are vector-based word representations which map related words to closer vectors, being the most common feature used in deep learning in natural language processing (Augenstein, et al. 2018). This is a feature that works well especially if the embeddings are trained on a corpus within the same domain, e.g. word embeddings used to classify Twitter comments should be trained on Twitter corpora for better performance (Stammbach, et al. 2018).

7. **Topic extraction** Topic extraction consists of extracting and classifying the underlying topic addressed by the document. This comes up as a useful feature in hate speech detection since certain topics are more commonly addressed than others in this type of discourse (e.g. Race, Religion, Politics) (Agarwal and Sureka, 2017). In Wiedemann et al. (2018), the users mentioned in the corpus are identified and their tweets are collected and the most probable topic is extracted.

8. **User profiling** Unlike all the features mentioned above, user profiling targets the users themselves instead of the actual text. This is a technique that hasn't been much explored, but

might output interesting results. Different approaches can be conducted in order to model users, including users interactions within social networks, their behavior, etc. In Pitsilis et al. (2018), the users' tendency towards a specific behavior (racism or sexism) is computed. In Qian et al. (2018) the inter and intra user representation is also considered.

9. Dictionaries: This feature consists of comparing the data corpus to a dictionary containing words of some kind, depending on the final objective. This might be a useful feature in hate speech detection, considering there's often an uncommon frequency of profane words (Dadvar et al., 2012). A common approach is to collect a set of swear words and check for their presence in the tweets (Salminen, et al. 2018; Scheffler, et al. 2018).

2.3 Training

Supervised learning is an important technique for solving classification problems. Training the classifier makes it easier for future predictions for unknown data.

2.4 Algorithms and performance metrics

Sentiment Analysis in text is mostly a supervised classification machine learning problem. Although the range of algorithms for such problems is quite wide, there is a smaller subset that performs better on text classification, thus being used more often. Figure 2 summarizes the frequency of algorithms used on automatic hate speech detection in text. Since deep learning has a wide range of possible architectures, neural network approaches were merged together.

The algorithms used in the literature are summarized in the paragraphs below:

- a) **Support Vector Machines:** SVM's are widely used in classification problems and the algorithm can be described as a hyperplane that categorizes input data (text in this case) (Chapelle, 2007; Bennett and Bredensteiner, 2000). In 2017, SVM's held the best results for text classification tasks, but in 2018 deep learning took over, especially in sentiment detection as described by Watanabe et al. (2018). Support vector machine analyzes the data, define the decision boundaries and uses the kernels for computation which are performed in input space (Mathur et al., 2018). The input data are two sets of vectors of size m each. Then every data which represented as a vector is classified into a class. Next we find a margin between the two classes that is far from any document. The distance defines the margin of the classifier, maximizing

the margin reduces indecisive decisions. SVM also supports classification and regression which are useful for statistical learning theory and it also helps recognizing the factors precisely, that needs to be taken into account, to understand it successfully.

- b) **Logistic Regression:** Logistic regression is a (predictive) regression analysis which estimates the parameters of a logistic model, a statistical model that uses a logistic function to model a binary dependant variable (Sperandei, 2014).
- c) **Random Forest:** Random forests are a combination of tree predictors such that each tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently and with the same distribution for all trees in the forest (Breiman, 2001). This model requires almost no input preparation, performs implicit feature selection and is very quick to train, performing well overall.
- d) **Naive Bayes:** This is an algorithm based on the Bayes' theorem with strong naive independence assumptions between the features of the data. It generally assumes that a particular feature in a class is unrelated to any other feature. Naive Bayes is a model useful for large datasets and does well despite being a simple method (Kaur and Oberai, 2014). Let d be the tweet and c^* be a class that is assigned to d , where

$$a. C^* = \arg \max_c P_{NB}(c|d) \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

$$b. P_{NB}(c|d) = \frac{(P(c)) \prod_{i=1}^m p(f_i|c)^{n_{i(d)}}}{p(d)} \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

- c. From the above equation, ' f ' is a 'feature' count of feature (f_i) is denoted with $n_{i(d)}$ and is present in d which represents a tweet. Here, m denotes number of features. Parameters $P(c)$ and $P(f/c)$ are computed through maximum likelihood estimates, and smoothing is utilized for unseen features. To train and classify using Naïve Bayes Machine Learning technique, we can use the Python NLTK library
- e) **Decision Tree:** This is an algorithm that provides support for decision making, providing a tree-like model of decisions and their possible consequences and other measures (e.g. resource cost, utility). They are often used since their output is usually readable, being simple to understand and interpret by humans. They are also fast and perform well on large datasets, but they are prone to overfitting (Topîrceanu and Grosseck, 2017).
- f) **Gradient Boosting:** This is a prediction model consisting of an ensemble of weak prediction models, typically decision trees (that's why it may also be called gradient

boosted trees), in which the predictions are not made independently (as in Bagging), but sequentially. The sequential modeling allows for each model to learn from the mistakes made by the previous one (Natekin and Knoll, 2013).

- g) **Maximum Entropy:** In Maximum Entropy Classifier, no assumptions are taken regarding the relationship between the features extracted from dataset. This classifier always tries to maximize the entropy of the system by estimating the conditional distribution of the class label. Maximum entropy even handles overlap feature and is same as logistic regression method which finds the distribution over classes. The conditional distribution is defined as MaxEnt makes no independence assumptions for its features, unlike Naive Bayes.

The model is represented by the following:

$$P_{ME}(c|d, \lambda) = \frac{\exp[\sum_i \lambda_i f_i(c, d)]}{\sum_c \exp[\sum_i \lambda_i f_i(c, d)]} \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

Where c is the class, d is the tweet and λ_i is the weight vector. The weight vectors decide the importance of a feature in classification.

Deep learning popularity has been growing significantly over the recent years, especially in text classification. This is partly due to the disclosure of artificial neural networks' architecture, which made it possible and easier to tune the parameters and, consequently, model the behavior of such algorithms. This produced better results, outperforming baseline algorithms. The main artificial neural networks' architectures are described below:

- a) **CNN**, convolutional neural networks are a class of deep feed-forward artificial neural networks. A CNN consists of an input and output layer and multiple hidden layers which consist of convolutional layers, pooling layers and fully connected layers (Yin et al., 2017).
- b) **RNN**, recurrent neural networks, another class of artificial neural networks that, unlike CNN's, are able to handle sequential data, allowing to produce temporal dynamic behaviors according to a time sequence. The connections between nodes form a directed graph. RNN's have feedback loops in the recurrent layer, which act as a memory mechanism. Despite this fact, long-term temporal dependencies are hard to grasp by the standard architecture, because the gradient of the loss function decays exponentially with time (vanishing gradient problem, Hochreiter (1998)). For this reason, new architectures have been introduced:

- c) **LSTM**, long short-term memory neural networks, are a type of RNN that use special units in addition to standard units, by including a memory cell able to keep information in memory for long periods of time. A set of gates is used to control when information enters the memory, when it's output, and when it's forgotten enabling this architecture to learn longer-term dependencies as detailed in Chung et al. (2014) and Yin et al. (2017).
- d) **GRU**, gated recurrent unit neural networks, are similar to LSTM's, but their structure is slightly simpler. Although they also use a set of gates to control the flow of information, these are fewer when compared to LSTM's Yin et al. (2017) and Chung et al. (2014).

Although both single directional LSTM and GRU's neural network architectures are able to handle sequential data, they fail to consider the contextual information from the future tokens. Thus, bidirectional architectures, BiLSTM and BiGRU, were introduced, where the algorithm is fed with the original data from the beginning to the end and vice-versa. Processing the sequence on two opposite directions allows the neural network to consider both the previous and future context of a single token as described in Liu et al. (2016).

According to the descriptions provided above, one would conclude that RNNs would perform better on text classification versus CNNs, considering words are usually connected within a context.

2.4.1 Performance Metrics

A wide range of performance metrics are used to evaluate machine learning algorithms and models. These measures are originally built from a confusion matrix (see Table 2) that, despite not being a performance measure by itself, serves as the basis for a number of other methods. The confusion matrix records which samples of the data have been correctly and incorrectly predicted for each class (Sokolova et al., 2006).

Table 2: Confusion matrix extracted from Sokolova et al. (2006)

Class \ Recognized as	Positive	Negative
Positive	True Positives (TP)	False Negatives (FN)
Negative	False Positives (FP)	True Negatives (TN)

Accuracy is a generic performance measure that assesses the overall effectiveness of the algorithm, by computing the number of correct predictions over all the predictions made. Although it is commonly used, accuracy doesn't distinguish between different classes (Sokolova et al., 2006). Consequently, this performance metric may be misleading, especially when the classes of the data are unbalanced (Harrell, 2017).

There is a subset of performance metrics that consider classes (e.g. Recall, Precision and Specificity). These are usually more useful in sets of data that contain unbalanced classes, since the performance of the algorithm can be assessed class wise. This is quite often in opinion mining datasets. The most used class wise, performance measures in sentiment detection are:

- a) **Recall**, also known as Sensitivity or True Positive Rate, is defined as the proportion of real positives that are correctly predicted as positive (Powers, 2008).
- b) **Precision** denotes the proportion of predicted positive cases that are actually positive (Powers, 2008).

The most used performance metric in text is the F1 score. It is defined as the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, and considers class imbalance, unlike accuracy (Sasaki, 2007), hence it's wide usage in sentiment analysis. Table 3 summarizes the most common performance metrics used in hate speech detection, including their formula and most frequent usage.

Using the above mentioned performance metrics, a graphical visualization of the algorithm's predictions can be computed, known as ROC, receiver operating characteristic. It shows the relation between the sensitivity and the specificity of the algorithm and is created by plotting the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) (Sokolova et al., 2006). The higher the TPR, the higher the area under ROC, also known as AUC (area under curve), as described in Powers (2008).

The results obtained by the state of the art experiments for sentiment detection in text are quite wide and rely on several different parameters. The tools chosen, libraries used and, mainly, the distribution and characteristics of the data used in the experiments contribute to produce a variety of results, which are often not comparable. Thus, and since we cannot

guarantee full uniformity in the procedures used in each experiment, we can at least make sure the datasets used are the same for each comparison we perform, ensuring a certain degree of viability.

Table 3: Description of performance metrics and their formulas. TP: True Positives, TN: True Negatives, FP: False Positives, FN: False Negatives.

	Formula	Common usage (Shung (March, 2018))
Accuracy	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$	Balance between Precision and Recall
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	High FP cost
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	High FN cost
F1 score	$\frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$	Balance between Precision and Recall for unbalanced classes

3. CHALLENGES IN SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Sentiment Analysis is a very challenging task. Following are some of the challenges faced in sentiment analysis of social media networks.

a. Identifying subjective parts of text: Subjective parts represent sentiment-bearing content. The same word can be treated as subjective in one case, or an objective in some other. This makes it difficult to identify the subjective portions of text.

For **example:**

- i. The language of the Mr. Amir was very crude.
- ii. Crude oil exploration is going on the northern Nigeria.

The word ‘crude’ is used as an opinion in first example, while it is completely objective in the second example.

b. Domain dependence: The same sentence or phrase can have different meanings in different domains. For

Example, the word “unpredictable” is positive in the domain of movies, dramas, etc, but if the same word is used in the context of a vehicle's steering, then it has a negative opinion.

c. Sarcasm Detection: Sarcastic sentences express negative opinion about a target using positive words in unique way.

Example: “Nice perfume. You must shower in it.”

The sentence contains only positive words but actually it expresses a negative sentiment.

d. Thwarted expressions: There are some sentences in which only some part of text determines the overall polarity of the document.

Example: “This Movie should be amazing. It sounds like a great plot, the popular actors, and the supporting cast are all talented.”

In this case, a simple bag-of-words approach will term it as positive sentiment, but the ultimate sentiment is negative.

e. Explicit Negation of sentiment: Sentiment can be negated in many ways as opposed to using simple no, not, never, etc. It is difficult to identify such negations.

Example: “It avoids all suspense and predictability found in Hollywood movies.”

Here the words suspense and predictable bear a negative sentiment, the usage of “avoids” negates their respective sentiments.

f. Order dependence: Discourse Structure analysis is essential for Sentiment Analysis/Opinion Mining.

Example: A is better than B, conveys the exact opposite opinion from, B is better than A.

g. Entity Recognition: There is a need to separate out the text about a specific entity and then analyze sentiment towards it.

Example: “I hate Microsoft, but I like Linux”.

A simple bag-of-words approach will label it as neutral; however, it carries a specific sentiment for both the entities present in the statement.

h. Building a classifier for subjective vs. objective tweets: Current research work focuses mostly on classifying positive vs. negative correctly. There is need to look at classifying opinions with sentiment vs. no sentiment closely.

i. Handling comparisons: Bag of words model doesn't handle comparisons very well.

Example: BUK is better than most of the private colleges”, the post would be considered positive for both BUK and private colleges using bag of words model because it doesn't take into account the relation towards “better”.

j. Applying sentiment analysis to Facebook messages: There has been less work on sentiment analysis on Facebook data mainly due to various restrictions by Facebook graph API and security policies in accessing data.

k. Internationalization: Current Research work focus mainly on English content, but social media networks has many varied users from across the globe.

4. TOOLS

There are no dedicated tools for sentiment analysis. Instead, a variety of tools are available for sentiment analysis.

A. *Python Natural Language Tool Kit (NLTK)*

It offers libraries for classification, tokenization, stemming etc. and lexical resources such as wordnet, sentiwordnet.

B. *RapidMiner,*

It is written in java. It holds up all steps for machine learning process like data preparation, results visualization, validation and optimization.

C. *R,*

It has a number of packages for sentiment analysis e.g. TM package and R Sentiment.

D. *Gate,*

It stands for General Architecture for Text Engineering. It has a set of modules tokenizer, gazetter, sentence splitter, part of speech tagger and named entities transducer etc.

E. *Weka,*

It is a collection of machine learning algorithm and visualization tools.

F. *Lingpipe,*

It provides a tool kit for analysis and synthesis of natural languages.

There are different data sources available for sentiment analysis.

1) *Blogs:* Expressing views through blogs is a common thing in today's world.

2) *Online Reviews:* Online reviews for a product can be gathered from e-commerce websites like www.amazon.com. Movie review data is available online is MDS (multi domain sentiment) data.

3) *Facebook:* Opinion is present in form of short messages like status on Facebook which can be used for the task of sentiment analysis.

4) *Twitter*: Twitter is a popular micro blogging website. It is broadly used to convey the opinion about any entity among all social networking sites. The maximum limit of character is 140 in twitter.

5) *Youtube*: Millions of video are uploaded on youtube. People give their opinion of these videos via comments. These comments can be extracted by using API.

6) *Email*: Email is the popular communication medium. The number of email users reached 2672 million as at 2016. Sentiment analysis can be done on personal email, office email, feedback email and business email etc.

7) *Forum*: Forum is an online discussion website where users can express their thoughts and views.

8) *News*: News is also a good source of opinion.

5. APPLICATIONS OF SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Sentiment analysis can be used in diverse fields for various purposes. Some of the common ones are given below.

1. *Applications that use Reviews from Websites*, such as sentiment analysis system that can extract sentiments about a particular product or services. It will help automate feedback or rating for a given product, item, etc.

2. *Applications as a Sub-component Technology*, as used in recommender systems. The recommender system will not recommend items that receive a lot of negative feedback or fewer ratings.

In online communication, we come across abusive language and other negative elements. These can be detected simply by identifying a highly negative sentiment and correspondingly taking action against it.

3. *Applications in Business Intelligence*, for many businesses, the online opinion decides the success or failure of their product since people nowadays tend to look upon reviews of products which are available online before they buy them. Thus, Sentiment Analysis plays an important role in businesses. Businesses also wish to extract sentiment from the online reviews in order to improve their products and in turn their reputation and help in customer satisfaction.

4. *Applications across Domains*, Recent researches in sociology and other fields like medical, sports have also benefitted from Sentiment Analysis that show trends in human emotions especially on social media.

5. *Applications In Smart Home*, Smart homes are supposed to be the technology of the future. In future entire homes would be networked and people would be able to control any part of the home using a tablet device. Recently there has been lot of research going on Internet of Things (IoT). Sentiment Analysis would also find its way in IoT. Like for example, based on the current sentiment or emotion of the user, the home could alter its ambiance to create a soothing and peaceful environment.

Sentiment Analysis can also be used in trend prediction. By tracking public views, important data regarding sales trends and customer satisfaction can be extracted.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we provide a survey and comparative study of existing techniques for opinion mining including machine learning and lexicon-based approaches, together with cross domain and cross-lingual methods and some evaluation metrics. Research results show that machine learning methods, such as SVM and naive Bayes have the highest accuracy and can be regarded as the baseline learning methods, while lexicon-based methods are very effective in some cases, which require little effort in human-labelled document. We also studied the effects of various features on classifier. We can conclude that more the cleaner data, more accurate results can be obtained. Use of bigram model provides better sentiment accuracy as compared to other models. We can focus on the study of combining machine learning method into opinion lexicon method in order to improve the accuracy of sentiment classification and adaptive capacity to variety of domains and different languages.

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Author(s)

1

Adamu Adamu Habu

He is currently an academic staff of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, University Bauchi (Nigeria), in the department of Mathematical Science.

2

S.K. Alaramma

He is currently an academic staff of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, University Bauchi (Nigeria), in the department of Mathematical Science.

3

B.I. Ya'u

He is currently an academic staff of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, University Bauchi (Nigeria), in the department of Mathematical Science.

4

S.W. Mustapha

He is currently an academic staff of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, University Bauchi (Nigeria), in the department of Mathematical Science.

5

M. A. Musa

He is currently an academic staff of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, University Bauchi (Nigeria), in the department of Mathematical Science.

